

VIRTUAL REALITY IS THE NEW APPROACH AND LATEST METHOD OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract. *The main aim of the article is to describe new learning technology VR in learning foreign languages, to state the great importance of IT in the process of studying. Besides that, one serious problem arises with people who have physical disorders and who inhabit distinct places to catch. That is why, the utilization of VR in education system creates so much meaning for us. The new method called beg studying improve life. Does VR really have the ability to ease the process of learning foreign language?*

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In order to stay connected to the contemporary world our education system is required to implement new technologies. In this case, Virtual Reality is the next logical step in the development of the Education System. VR is the tool for delivering what is known as experiential learning. The education theory is based on the idea that we learn and remember things much better when we practice something by ourselves rather than by simply observing someone else do it or being told about it. According to the resent experiment have been carried by professor Ann Schlosser at the University of Washington, VR even has the ability to make the development of false memories happen. Since involvement is a key point in helping students not only learn more quickly but also remain what they learned. These powers can be harnessed in teaching and learning foreign languages. Mondly's CEO, Alex Iliescu said that: "The biggest things that keep people from actually speaking and using new languages are fear and lack of life-like practice. We're filling the conversational gap of traditional language education." The average language learner normally takes up to about 5-7 months before trying to begin a conversation. But with VR the fear of not speak is reduced. If you talk with a responsive character that looks like a human it will give learner to achieve the same result as real world. It feels like an actual conversation, but without any gadgets people will think you're sounding stupid. Expanded Teaching Possibilities Modern education system has issues with the limited ability to describe and explain ideas in a more practical and accessible manner. This approach of explaining things is usually miss affair where some students get the purpose while others are unable to try and do that. While this is a lesser challenge in humanitarian sciences, it becomes essential when it comes to physics, programming language and foreign language. Another factor that might be greatly.

Improve learning language by implementation of VR is inclusively of the students with numerous disabilities into the academic method. For instance, now with the help of the VR they do not need to go to schools, extra lessons, special places like libraries or waiting conversation clubs which are once in a week. They will enroll curse by distance and can save their assets which is time. Another cool example can be "best friend" program. This program creates friend who can be seen only for you. If you talk by yourself people can think you are stupid but if you have friend who knows foreign language very well it would be very good for you to practice speaking skill. It will also provide them an opportunity to experience out-of-reach things, however it can be also very sensible in the everyday education process. One of the difficult thing in learning any skill is keeping attention of the classroom. Now we call them distractions. Shabin Sharma said so well

"Addiction to distraction is the loosen". Also in learning new foreign language people use their mobile devices. I do not have any judgments on that kind of IT technology but using them in the right way is key of success. VR gives opportunity to students avoid this kind of distractions in the leaning process. Well-orchestrated Virtual Reality experience can totally shut off the student's focus from any distracting factors and amp up his concentration on the subject considerably. You will only concentrate on learning new language after all lessons you can again use them as before. People used class room teaching method approximately 50 years ago. If you look our modern way of learning new language you can see the same method but a little bit changed. My English teacher N.Tillayeva said so well: "After teaching so many years students from all over the world I realized that there is no other way of learning foreign languages. Only practice, practice and practice". It is true, if you want to develop your writing skill set you should practice to write or if you want to increase your speech you should speak. And I really like feedback when it comes to learning a new language. Expect feedback from powerful technology will not only give suggestion improvements in terms of vocabulary but also provide support you become a more confident speaker.

In the process of a study the outline of all main information technologies used in learning foreign languages was given, the great importance of IT in the learning process as well as in the process of raising motivation among students was proven as well. Application of VR interactive technologies substantially improves the quality of lesson material and raises the motivation, at the same time individualizing the language learning. Taking into account all the above-mentioned factors we can draw a conclusion, that in the modern society, where it is difficult to surprise students by something, the use of VR can become an additional tool that will introduce the originality into the educational process, inspiring students for further creativity and motivate them to a higher level.

Therefore, the implementation VR in the educational process became one of the substantial parts of professional competence. Virtual Reality technology offers numerous exciting opportunities for learning foreign language. Save your time and practice with VR you will reach to high new level.

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